

Giant Epithelial Splenic Cyst Mimicking a Pancreatic Cystic Neoplasm: Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Splenic cysts are an uncommon entity, usually diagnosed incidentally due to their asymptomatic nature in clinical practice. Surgical treatment is essential in symptomatic cysts, those larger than 5 cm, or when malignancy cannot be excluded. Histopathological analysis is necessary to identify the splenic subtype and to rule out potential malignant transformation of the pluripotent epithelium. This report presents the case of a patient with a true giant splenic cyst that mimicked a pancreatic cystic neoplasm, diagnosed in the General Surgery Department of the High Specialty Medical Unit No. 25 of the Mexican Institute of Social Security. A 41-year-old woman presented with left upper quadrant abdominal pain, accompanied by postprandial fullness and weight loss, due to an 18 cm tumor causing a mass effect. CT imaging revealed a pancreatic cystic lesion, displacement of other intra-abdominal organs, and the presence of an accessory spleen. The patient was scheduled for surgical treatment due to the tumor size, with planned laparotomy, distal pancreatectomy, and splenectomy. However, based on intraoperative findings, total and accessory splenectomy and resection of the splenic cyst were performed. Histopathological examination confirmed an epithelial splenic cyst, negative for malignancy.

Objective: To document the presentation of a splenic cyst as an intraoperative finding and describe the subsequent definitive surgical treatment.

Materials and Methods: Descriptive observational study. A literature review was conducted on the PubMed platform, including reported cases from 2020 to 2025.

KEYWORDS: Splenic cyst, spleen, splenectomy, case report, Mexico.

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INTRODUCTION

Splenic cysts are rare lesions of the spleen. Worldwide, the most common cause is parasitic origin, especially in underdeveloped countries, followed by post-traumatic lesions. True congenital cysts account for less than 10% of cases. A systematic diagnostic approach is required, involving imaging studies and histopathological analysis for optimal classification and therapeutic decision-making. Surgical intervention remains the cornerstone of treatment, with increasing emphasis on spleen-preserving techniques. Generally, the therapeutic goal is to relieve symptoms and prevent complications. Conservative management is appropriate for small, asymptomatic cysts, while

laparoscopic partial splenectomy is the recommended procedure when the size and location of the cyst allow for the preservation of at least 25% of the splenic parenchyma, thereby maintaining immunological protection and preventing infectious complications such as post-splenectomy sepsis syndrome. Otherwise, total splenectomy becomes inevitable. This procedure, performed in cysts larger than 10 cm and/or those involving the splenic hilum, yields good outcomes in experienced hands and should be considered the treatment of choice.

We present the second case of a primary splenic cyst diagnosed in the past eight years in the General Surgery Department of the High Specialty Medical Unit No. 25,

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IMSS, and provide a review of the medical literature offering information on the epidemiology, etiology, pathogenesis, classification, diagnostic evaluation, and treatment modalities of this entity.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 41-year-old female patient, with no significant clinical history, infections, or trauma, began presenting symptoms in May 2023 with colicky abdominal pain located in the left hypochondrium, accompanied by unintentional weight loss and early postprandial fullness. Physical examination revealed a mass in the left upper quadrant. Laboratory tests were within normal limits, including CA 19-9 level at 12.4 U/mL. A triple-phase abdominal CT scan showed a large, ovoid lesion in the body and tail of the pancreas, with defined borders, thin wall, unilocular, homogeneous fluid attenuation (12 HU), without abnormal enhancement. The lesion caused significant thinning of the pancreatic parenchyma, without visualization of septations or calcifications, measuring $18.1 \times 11.9 \times 10.5$ cm. Given its characteristics, a mucinous cystadenoma was suspected. The approximate volume was 1176 cc, causing a mass effect on adjacent structures, compressing and displacing the stomach anteriorly and laterally, the spleen and left kidney inferiorly, and the splenic vein. The duodenum and jejunum were displaced to the right hemiabdomen. A lobulated image with defined borders, isodense to splenic tissue, with arterial supply from the splenic artery, measuring 9.2×3.1 cm, was observed in the upper pole of the spleen, consistent with an accessory spleen (Figures 1 and 2).

Figure 1 and 2. Triple-phase abdominopelvic CT scan, axial (1) and coronal (2) views, showing a giant cyst of apparent pancreatic origin compressing and displacing the stomach, left kidney, spleen, and small intestine.

Surgical management was indicated via laparotomy with distal pancreatectomy and splenectomy. Under balanced general anesthesia and in the supine position, a Chevron incision was performed, and the abdominal cavity was entered in layers. Intraoperative findings included a cystic tumor dependent on the spleen measuring approximately 18×10 cm with adhesions to the cardia and left diaphragmatic crus, displacing the body and tail of the pancreas and an accessory spleen located at the splenic hilum (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Surgical splenectomy specimen showing accessory spleen at the upper pole of the spleen.

Given these findings, a total and accessory splenectomy along with cyst resection was decided (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Intraoperative findings: firm adhesions between the splenic cyst and diaphragm.

Adhesiolysis was performed; the gastro-splenic ligament was divided to access the lesser sac. The spleen was then mobilized by dividing the splenocolic ligament and short gastric vessels; the splenic artery and vein were individually ligated and divided using 2-0 silk. The specimen was extracted. Dissection of the retroperitoneal cyst followed using monopolar energy. The tail and body of the pancreas were retracted. Upon manipulation, the cyst ruptured, releasing yellowish, non-fetid fluid without debris, which was aspirated. Dissection continued, releasing adhesions of the cyst capsule to the diaphragmatic crus and gastric cardia. A 60 mm linear stapler was used for division, and the specimen was extracted. Abdominal wall closure was performed in layers: continuous aponeurotic suture with 1-0 Vicryl, inverted stitches with 2-0 Vicryl in the subcutaneous tissue, and titanium staples to approximate the skin. Total blood loss was 100 cc. Histopathological examination of the specimen

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revealed a 10 × 8 cm epithelial splenic cyst, negative for malignancy (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Microscopic image of the cyst showing epithelial lining of the cyst wall (H&E, 40x).

The patient had a favorable postoperative course; symptoms resolved completely, and she was discharged on postoperative day two with follow-up scheduled in the outpatient clinic. Pneumococcal and meningococcal vaccines were administered during the first postoperative week. At present, the patient remains asymptomatic.

DISCUSSION

Splenic cysts are rare benign lesions of the spleen, often asymptomatic and discovered incidentally during imaging studies (1). The most widely used classification in clinical practice is Martin's (1958), which categorizes them as primary and secondary. Primary cysts are further divided into parasitic and non-parasitic; the latter are then classified as congenital or neoplastic. Another classification, proposed by Fowler in 1913, distinguishes parasitic cysts (the most frequent), mainly caused by *Echinococcus granulosus* (hydatid disease), and non-parasitic cysts (2). Non-parasitic cysts include true or primary cysts, which represent around 10% of cases, have an epithelial or mesothelial lining, and arise from congenital anomalies. Their pathogenesis involves mesothelial invagination during embryonic development, with possible subsequent squamous metaplasia. Various epithelial types can be found, such as epidermoid (the most common and the one reported in this case), mesothelial, serous, and transitional. Pseudocysts or secondary cysts, which make up 70–80% of cases, lack epithelial lining and usually arise after trauma, infarction, or prior splenic infections (3). It is proposed that trauma causes intraparenchymal hemorrhage or a subcapsular splenic hematoma, leading to liquefaction and fibrous capsule formation without cellular lining. Eventually, cellular contents settle in the walls, and the fluid becomes serous and clear.

Another widely accepted classification is that of Morgenstern (2002), for non-parasitic splenic cystic lesions (4), dividing them according to etiology into congenital (epithelial, epidermoid, and mesothelial), neoplastic (endothelial origin, lymphangioma, hemangioma, primary cystic tumors, and metastatic tumors), traumatic (subcapsular hematoma), necrotic (due to infections such as endocarditis, typhoid fever,

generalized infectious lymphadenopathy, mononucleosis), and degenerative (cystified splenic infarcts).

The incidence of splenic cysts is low, ranging from 0.07% to 0.13%. The first case was documented by Andral in 1929, and currently fewer than 1,000 cases have been reported worldwide, making them a rarity in clinical practice (5). Their prevalence has increased due to more frequent detection through imaging studies. Congenital cysts are more common in young women (60%), with a female-to-male ratio of 8:1, and show hormonal influence related to pregnancy and menstruation, whereas post-traumatic pseudocysts show no sex predilection. The age of presentation ranges from newborns to individuals in their 50s, with the second and third decades being the most common time of manifestation. They are typically solitary and primarily located in the upper pole of the spleen (6).

Most splenic cysts are asymptomatic in 30–60% of cases and are discovered incidentally. Larger cysts (>4–5 cm) can cause symptoms due to compression of adjacent structures (5). The most common symptoms include pain in the left upper quadrant, fullness, nausea, vomiting, and weight loss secondary to displacement and pressure on the stomach or splenic flexure of the colon. Respiratory symptoms such as pleuritic pain and dyspnea can also occur due to restriction of diaphragmatic movement, as well as urinary symptoms like proteinuria and hypertension caused by renal or ureteropelvic compression (7).

Diagnosis is based on clinical history, physical examination, and imaging studies. Evaluation of tumor markers such as CEA and CA 19-9 can help identify epidermoid cysts, as their epithelium may secrete these markers. Cases have been reported with elevated serum and cyst fluid levels of these markers. These values usually normalize 30 to 60 days after cyst resection (8). Abdominal ultrasound is the initial tool due to its accessibility and its ability to characterize cyst types: hydatid cysts tend to be multiple and multivesicular and may also be found in the liver or lungs; true cysts are usually solitary, anechoic, and show no internal blood flow, in contrast with lymphomas or hemangiomas which exhibit positive Doppler signal. CT and MRI are the preferred imaging modalities, as they provide detailed information about the location, size, and anatomical relationships of the cyst, allowing differentiation between simple cysts and more complex lesions, and facilitating treatment planning (9).

The therapeutic approach depends on cyst size, presence of symptoms, and risk of complications. Small, asymptomatic cysts may be managed conservatively with periodic imaging. However, surgical treatment is essential in symptomatic cysts, those larger than 5 cm, or when malignancy cannot be excluded (5). Options include total splenectomy for giant, multiple cysts, or those located at the splenic hilum or completely covered by parenchyma. Spleen-preserving techniques have been highlighted in reports by Zografos et al. and Geraghty et al., emphasizing advancements in minimally invasive surgery such as partial splenectomy or partial

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decapsulation via laparoscopy. These approaches offer reduced morbidity and aim to preserve splenic function and reduce the risk of post-splenectomy sepsis caused by *Streptococcus pneumoniae* and other encapsulated organisms such as *Haemophilus influenzae* (11,12). Alternative techniques have occasionally been described, such as marsupialization (associated with a high rate of infectious complications), sclerotherapy (with a high recurrence rate), and cyst unroofing when a portion of the cyst wall is not in contact with splenic parenchyma, also performed laparoscopically. However, up to 64% of these cases recur within the first year. For follow-up, ultrasound and CA 19-9 measurement are recommended three months postoperatively to exclude cyst recurrence. In conservatively managed cases, annual ultrasound for five years is advised to monitor for growth (12).

Their clinical relevance lies in their potential complications such as spontaneous rupture, infection, chemical peritonitis, intracystic hemorrhage, hypersplenism, and portal hypertension (13). Total splenectomy remains the gold standard treatment (14). The importance of this case lies in the uncommon spontaneous occurrence of a splenic cyst that radiologically mimicked a pancreatic cystic tumor (mucinous cystadenoma).

CONCLUSION

In this case, we faced the challenge of a true splenic cyst requiring surgical intervention due to its size and mass effect. Although a pancreatic cystic neoplasm was initially suspected, intra-splenic pancreatic pseudocysts can erode into the spleen, mimicking a splenic origin. Diagnosis remains challenging to this day and requires careful evaluation to determine the need for intervention, as management lacks a clear algorithm due to its low incidence particularly in the absence of prior abdominal trauma, parasitic infection, or degenerative disease. The complexity of the approach and management of splenic cysts becomes even more evident in this case, where a large epithelial splenic cyst was initially misidentified as a probable mucinous cystadenoma. This underscores the critical role of differential diagnosis in splenic lesions and justifies further research to establish evidence-based protocols that optimize diagnostic and therapeutic strategies to prevent complications and improve quality of life. Although spleen-preserving techniques could be considered depending on the cyst's location and remaining splenic parenchyma developed to avoid post-splenectomy sepsis syndrome the chosen surgical approach was total splenectomy due to the cyst's size. We emphasize the importance of a multidisciplinary approach, involving radiologists, pathologists, and surgeons, for comprehensive management of splenic cysts.

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